

Improving the Cost-Efficiency of Oil and Gas E&P Activities: The Machine Learning as a Perspective for the Sonatrach

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Summary

Reports suggest that crude oil and gas product consumption and demand will continue to increase. This underscores the importance of innovation in the hydrocarbon sector to optimize exploration and production activities and manage costs. In a competitive and risky environment, "Machine Learning" tools are revolutionizing the oil industry by efficiently processing vast amounts of data without relying on predefined rules. These data-driven models will help address technical and economic challenges quickly. This paper explores projects in the hydrocarbon E&P industry that utilize "Machine Learning" tools, showcasing their benefits. The Sonatrach can get inspired from these experiences for potential application in future projects and investments.

Keywords: Exploration, Production, Data Science, Machine Learning, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Prediction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The hydrocarbon sector is currently being reshaped by cutting-edge technologies, which are considered as the driving forces of any modern economy. With the advent of the digital revolution and the vast amount of data available, industrial players, particularly Oil & Gas (O&G) companies, are making significant investments, focusing on training, and establishing partnerships. Their aim is to effectively harness these innovative tools to accomplish targets and maximize profits.

The oil price plummet in 2014 prompted hydrocarbon companies to increasingly embrace new technologies to optimize exploration and operational costs, enhance efficiency, and boost profitability. One of these transformative technologies is "Machine Learning", which O&G professionals are integrating into various partnership projects. According to McKinsey & Company, the adoption of "Machine Learning" and other "Big Data" solutions could potentially save the oil and gas industry up to \$50 billion over the next decade [1].

Machine Learning (ML) can be defined as the capability of computers or software applications to autonomously learn, draw conclusions, and establish logical patterns from data without explicit programming. The hydrocarbon industry generates an enormous amount of data throughout the entire value chain, especially in upstream activities, spanning exploration and development, from subsurface reservoirs to surface facilities, including wells and gathering networks. Rather than reacting to events, oil companies recognize the value of ML tools in generating predictive models and implementing proactive strategies based on existing data and lessons learned. These predictive models enable the industry to make unprecedented conclusions and diverse correlations, significantly benefiting Exploration and Production (E&P) activities.

Given the inherent uncertainty in the fossil energy sector, including factors like reserve discoveries, price volatility, and fluctuating demand, the Sonatrach must also leverage ML-based data analytics. This approach will allow the Sonatrach achieving its multiple objectives and meeting market expectations. The choice made by O&G companies such as Gazprom, Exxon Mobil, and Equinor to step into the field of ML is wise and deserves to be considered for possible implementation of ML-based industrial projects. Instead of venturing alone into this very demanding technical domain, they have opted to partner with high-tech firms, such as Microsoft, Nvidia or Google Cloud, having and

providing a wide range of ML and artificial intelligence (AI) solutions. This strategic choice has led to outstanding achievements and a lot of expertise have been gained as a consequence by their engineers and researchers.

The objective of this contribution is not to provide an exhaustive overview of Machine Learning methods applied in the hydrocarbon Exploration & Production (E&P) sector. Instead, it seeks to highlight the achievements of Oil & Gas professionals using ML to address various technical and industrial challenges. This papers also aims to show to the audience, especially the SH engineers and managers what kind of problems can be solved using ML and what is the best way forward to implement ML-based solutions as part of an industrial project.

2. DATA SCIENCE - The 4th PARADIGM

The realm of technology and science has long borne witness to numerous changes through which engineers, theorists, researchers, and humanity as a whole have managed to conceive and envision the fundamental tools and principles necessary to address concerns of their epoch [2]. The 4th paradigm of science and technology emerged due to the proliferation of information systems and data acquisition tools, data transfer networks (internet and intranet networks), as well as data processing and modeling techniques based on statistical concepts.

Before that, humanity relied on its observation and interpretation abilities - this was the 1st paradigm or the era of experience - to comprehend and harness certain phenomena (such as fire for heat production or cooking, wind for sea travel, etc.). Subsequently, with the development of human thinking and the discovery of mathematics, physical phenomena were formulated in terms of theories and equations (Bernoulli equation to describe fluid flow, Maxwell equations for electromagnetism, etc.). This was the 2nd paradigm (Theoretical Sciences). As time progressed, some models became too complex to solve, and with the emergence of high-powered computational machines (computers), it became possible to numerically solve 3D or 4D differential equations, such as the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) equations for instance (3rd paradigm - Numerical Computations).

Over the past 20 years, the 4th paradigm has been brought forward thanks to the continuous development of computing infrastructures, database management systems, and data processing tools. This development has been driven by the increase in the volume of data available to professionals, the digitalization of various industrial activities, and the deployment of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), Big Data solutions, and Cloud Computing [3]. This digital revolution has, in turn, brought forth solutions to new challenges that cannot be solved with classical approaches (analytical and/or numerical solutions).

3. MACHINE LEARNING CATEGORIES

Machine Learning is another way of solving problems using data without an a priori knowledge of the physics or the logic behind them. It relies on some concepts of statistics to extract knowledge and infer meaningful insights; and it has been used to investigate or find solution to technical or non-technical problems (Medicine, criminology, sociology, sport, marketing, etc.) where analytical and/or numerical models cannot or are not able to solve those problems. The benefits for the O&G industry from ML revolves around two major ML categories: "Supervised Learning" and "Unsupervised Learning." It's important to understand their principle, type of problems they can sort out, and limitations of their algorithms.

3.1. Learning Types

3.1.1. Supervised Learning

This purpose of this type of learning is to find correlations between an output (target) and inputs (predictors). The model, i.e.; the ML algorithm, learns to map inputs to outputs and can make

predictions on new, unseen data. There are two main subcategories pertaining to "Supervised Learning": regression and classification. When the output variable is a numeric variable (e.g., rock permeability [4]), "Regression" will be used for prediction. On the other hand, when the output variable is categorical (e.g., lithofacies type [5]), we refer to as "Classification".

3.1.2. Unsupervised Learning

This type of ML is employed when the goal is to uncover various correlations that may exist among a set of variables or parameters. There is no target to predict and the algorithm that is used will help to find patterns or relationships within the data itself. The main applications that are generally encountered in "Unsupervised Learning" are "Clustering" and "Dimensionality Reduction". Clustering is applied to group similar data points together without predefined categories. Dimensionality reduction is preferred when we aim to reduce the number of variables while preserving essential information [6].

3.1.3. Reinforcement Learning

Mainly applied in prescriptive analytics, Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a machine learning paradigm focused on enabling software agents to make sequential decisions in dynamic environments. Unlike traditional supervised learning, RL does not require labeled datasets. Instead, agents learn by interacting with their environment, taking actions, and receiving feedback in the form of rewards or penalties. The primary goal of RL is for the agent to discover a strategy or policy that maximizes its cumulative reward over time. It has found applications in various domains, including robotics, game playing, flow allocation and some petroleum applications (flow allocation and well placement, CO₂ injection), making it a pivotal area within AI for autonomous decision-making and optimization.

3.2. Machine Learning Algorithms

Various algorithms are available for solving "Supervised Learning" and "Unsupervised Learning" problems, as illustrated in "Fig.1". The choice of a particular algorithm depends on the type of prediction to be performed (regression, classification), the size of the data as well as their type, i.e.; structured (tabulated format) or non-structured (pictures, photos).

Fig.1. Examples of machine learning algorithms

While it has been shown that certain algorithms, such as those belonging to "Ensemble Methods", including Gradient Boosting algorithms like XGBoost and LightGBM, are known to be powerful in terms of speed and accuracy, there's no pre-established guideline to assert that a particular algorithm will necessarily produce remarkable results. Usually it is by carrying out experiments, i.e.; by running simulations, that a practitioner will finally gain insights on the performance of the ML model being

used as well as the quality of the yielded results.

The development of ML solutions is primarily done using tools and libraries offered within programming languages such as Python, R, C++, Julia, or Matlab. These development environments offer several advantages, enabling engineers to develop codes in order to address technical challenges related to the hydrocarbon E&P activities. Additionally, commercial tools are already offered by companies such as Schlumberger, Emerson E&P, or Solution Seeker. These tools leverage the latest advancements in ML and cutting-edge technologies having significant computing power in terms of CPU, GPU, or TPU.

3.3. Machine Learning Workflow

The main steps to highlight when it comes to finding a solution to a problem through “Machine Learning” are shown in “Fig.2”.

Fig.2. Typical workflow of a machine learning predictive model

Any ML process starts with collecting or importing data, followed by data preparation. Data preparation involves. Data preparation (data conditioning, preprocessing) involves the following steps:

- Removing duplicate values.
- Handling missing values (e.g., using means, medians, or methods like KNN Imputation).
- Addressing outliers (using statistical methods or automated detection).
- Exploratory data analysis (EDA) to check how variables are correlated between them.
- Performing feature engineering (Converting categorical values to numerical, Normalizing data).
- Splitting data into training and test sets.

Once prepared, data is fed into an ML algorithm for training and testing on unseen data to evaluate performance. Hyperparameters tuning of the final ML model is a must-to-do step in order to get to an ideal ML model with improved prediction capabilities. At the end and once all the work is validated, the ML model can be deployed in order to make predictions on new data. Definitely, ML is an art and best practices guide practitioners toward accurate and reliable results when solving real-world problems.

4. APPLIED MACHINE LEARNING IN E&P - RESEARCH PROJECTS

The tools provided by ML have been utilized in the hydrocarbon E&P industry for nearly two decades [7]. Embracing and mastering these diverse tools can empower oil companies to maintain their competitiveness in exploration, reservoir development, operational planning, and production optimization. In the upcoming sections, we will delve into how ML techniques have been utilized by researchers and professionals in the hydrocarbon industry across various exploration and production disciplines.

4.1. Geosciences

Petroleum reservoir characterization is the result of a combined effort involving the analysis and interpretation of a variety of data obtained during exploration campaigns conducted by geologists for the study of rocks and outcrops, seismic survey campaigns carried out by geophysicists to locate hydrocarbon traps, and the interpretation of results from various well logging techniques led by petrophysicists. Therefore, a vast amount of data is generated downstream of each operation, and here comes the role of the ML approach to speed up data interpretation processing.

4.1.1. Geophysics

Seismic Interpretation: Deep Learning (DL) algorithms - DL being a subfield of ML - such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have been used for the reconstruction of seismic images with poor quality (or missing traces) and for the enhancement of image resolution [8]. Another application of GAN algorithms in the context of "Assisted Seismic Inversion" has been reported by Moser et al [9].

Salt Bodies Delineation: This task typically takes a considerable amount of time, and the degree of uncertainty is pretty low. Deep Learning algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) were proven to be efficient in the identification and delineation of salt bodies [10].

Seismic Fault Detection: Advanced research have enabled accurate identification of fault networks within petroleum systems from seismic images, thanks to the "Encoder-Decoder" CNN algorithms [11,12].

4.1.2. Reservoir Characterization

Facies Classification: Determining lithofacies from well-logs measurements is of utmost importance, especially when we want to identify hydrocarbon-rich layers. Support Vector Classifiers (SVCs) have demonstrated their capabilities in performing facies classification with considerable accuracy [13].

Petrophysical Characterization: Petrophysical properties of sedimentary environments and hydrocarbon reservoirs, such as porosity, permeability, and water saturation, are of paramount importance for building static models and estimating original hydrocarbon volumes in place. Once again, neural networks have been instrumental in generating synthetic logs for these petrophysical parameters because of the power they got to handle bigger datasets [14,15].

4.2. Drilling and Completion

Onshore or offshore drilling operations are known to be extremely expensive, where potential hazards to personnel, equipment, and the environment are always present. Optimizing capital expenditures (CAPEX) associated with drilling and completion activities, and thus ensuring safer operations during these two critical operations can be achieved using ML techniques. Through data history and real-time data, forecasts on future performance of key parameters can be made to anticipate unwanted events and take necessary measures.

4.2.1. Automated Events Detection

Various ML algorithms can be utilized to automatically identify and classify any type of event that may occur during drilling by analyzing changing trends in drilling parameters [16,17]. Algeria's extensive experience in drilling and the lessons learned over the decades can be leveraged, along with daily drilling reports and data transmitted by data acquisition devices (sensors) mounted on rig equipment. Predictive models can then be developed to anticipate any potential high-risk event [18,19]. Recently, a new approach combined the power and capabilities of data analytics, natural language processing (NLP) and ML to extract meaningful insights from daily drilling reports

(unstructured datasets). The AI-based solutions that was built helped engineers and decision-makers in well planning, risk assessment and planning mitigation solutions [20].

4.2.2. Minimizing Non-Productive Time

Minimizing Non-Productive Time (NPT) during drilling is a major concern for oil operators. NPT is typically caused by issues such as gas kicks and drill string sticking. Some research has highlighted the importance of applying ML concepts to prevent or reduce the likelihood of such incidents.

Gas Kicks: This issue can occur if the density of the drilling fluid - which acts as the primary barrier in case a blow-out occurs - is not adjusted or if the circulation rate is not appropriate (either too high or too low). Using data from the ongoing drilling operation, the application of ML techniques can help estimate optimal circulation rates and mud volumes to be pumped, enabling operators to take necessary measures before a potential gas kick occurs [21].

Preventing Stuck Drilling String: Drill string sticking is a recurring problem where drilling engineers need to anticipate and address it. Due to inherent nonlinearities, predicting the occurrence of this event has been achieved through the use of neural networks combined with optimization algorithms such as “Swarm Particle Optimization” [22].

4.3. Reservoir engineering

Reservoir engineers have unlimited access to data provided by geologists, petrophysicists, and producers. All this valuable information allows them to develop optimal scenarios for better reservoir management. Some examples of activities in which reservoir engineers can leverage ML techniques include the following.

4.3.1. Oil and Gas Fields Development

During the development phase, reservoir engineers use data from existing wells to plan the drilling of new wells (producers or injectors) and design their subsurface trajectories [23]. Due to the high number of parameters to consider as part of the placement and drilling of new wells, some studies [24,25] have combined Principal Component Analysis method (PCA - Unsupervised Learning) to reduce the number of variables along with regression methods (Supervised Learning) to predict the placement and flow potential of these new wells.

4.3.2. Assisted History Matching

Any “History Matching” process is known to be time-consuming due to the heterogeneities of some reservoirs (particularly in Algeria) and uncertainties. Neural networks as learning algorithm have been applied in “History Matching” duties, resulting in significant time savings compared to large computation durations usually taken by reservoir simulators [26,27].

4.3.3. Reserve Estimation and Production Forecasting

Besides other common conventional methods, “Decline Curve Analysis” (DCA) methods have always been used for reserve estimation and future well potential forecasting. Some papers emphasized the advantage of using neural networks to predict future flow performance of producer wells [28,29,30].

4.4. Production

The decline in hydrocarbon reservoirs' potential, including reservoir pressure and production rate, is inevitable over an oil field's lifespan. Common issues like reservoir damage, tubing problems (collapse, plugging, etc.), or equipment failures often arise. Predicting these problems is crucial for efficient reservoir management, extending well life, and reducing costly interventions and non-productive time.

4.4.1. Production Optimization

Neural network algorithms, such as Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs), have been proposed to identify potential faults across hydrocarbon supply chain and determine the probability of their occurrence [31]. These learning algorithms have successfully predicted integrity issues like water coning, wax deposits, and casing leaks, demonstrating outstanding performance. Additionally, other ML algorithms like Least-squares Support Vector Regression (LS-SVR) and Gaussian process regression (GPR) have been suggested for production optimization tasks, aiming to maximize NPV (Net-Present Value) from operational assets [32].

4.4.2. Completion Optimization

Oil and gas petroleum engineers have harnessed various databases to select the best completion for both conventional and non-conventional wells. Some practitioners employed ML algorithms like Random Forests (RF), Gradient Boosting (GBM, XGBoost) to create predictive models for determining optimal completion systems [33,34]. In another approach, a classification method was used to recommend the ideal sand control system. ML classifiers such as K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Classifiers (SVC), and Decision Tree (DT) Classifiers were employed for this purpose [35].

5. APPLIED MACHINE LEARNING PROJECTS IN PETROLEUM E&P INDUSTRY

5.1. ExxonMobil et le MIT

ExxonMobil has partnered with researchers at MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technologies) to automate hydrocarbon exploration and create AI-based autonomous robots for offshore exploration [36]. This collaboration aims to provide ExxonMobil with expertise in cutting-edge technologies.

MIT researchers collaborated with ExxonMobil engineers to develop AI software for subsea exploration robots, with ML as the core of these AI applications. These robots are designed to characterize the seabed and analyze outcrops to identify potential hydrocarbon traps. In the past, oil companies relied on diver teams and geological analysts for subsea exploration. ExxonMobil's use of autonomous underwater robots aims to reduce HSE risks associated with offshore exploration. This innovative use of ML and AI has the potential to lower offshore exploration costs for oil companies.

5.2. Baker Hughes & Nvidia

Baker Hughes' collaboration with Nvidia aims to harness specific databases and introduce ML and AI solutions to oil companies for an efficient utilization of available information and data. This encompasses seismic data, drilling reports, various logs, production data, and sensor-transmitted data. The goal is to optimize exploration and production costs, facilitate investment planning, and create additional value [35].

Baker Hughes has developed DL-based data analysis software to assist engineers and managers in decision-making. This software can predict equipment malfunctions or failures by analyzing production data and real-time data from pressure, flow, and temperature sensors.

5.3. Total & Google Cloud

Total has partnered with Google Cloud to collaboratively develop an AI-based system for analyzing exploration data. The objective is to enhance the efficiency of its E&P activities by reducing the time typically spent on manually analyzing seismic data, cutting costs, and rapidly assessing the quality of prospects in terms of reservoir quality and hydrocarbons in-place [37].

Total and Google are collaborating to develop an AI system that assists Total's geologists in interpreting subsurface seismic images through computer vision technology powered by an ML-

trained model. Additionally, they are working to automate the analysis of technical documents using natural language processing (NLP) technology. These objectives involve advanced neural network algorithms.

5.4. Solution Seeker – ENGIE & Wintershall

Norwegian start-up Solution Seeker has made a breakthrough by creating an AI-based solution that achieves real-time production optimization. They have developed an advanced neural network architecture with strong predictive capabilities specifically for real-time hydrocarbon production optimization [38].

Traditional ML algorithms are insufficient to address production optimization challenges. The dynamics of oil fields are complex, erratic, and ever-changing, with control parameters varying over time. Moreover, the high uncertainty of subsurface parameters (reservoir, wellbore) complicates the design of short- or long-term production strategies. The AI solution created by Solution Seeker was first deployed in 2018 on the Gjøa field (operated by ENGIE E&P) and on the Vega field (operated by Wintershall).

5.5. Gazprom & Yandex Terra

Gazprom and Yandex, Russia's leading Internet and high-tech company, have signed a cooperation agreement to initiate new projects across different sectors of the oil and gas industry [39]. Both companies aim to leverage recent advancements in AI and ML to create and implement innovative solutions within the oil and energy sector. This collaboration is expected to emphasize the improvement of the following:

- E&P data analysis and interpretation.
- Drilling and well completion operations.
- Production and refining operations, as well as fluid treatment.

5.6. Equinor & Ambyint

In 2017, Equinor acquired the AI solution offered by Ambyint with the aim of enhancing oil production performance from the shale deposits in the Bakken formations, located in North Dakota, USA. Ambyint's AI solution, named "Infinity" ®, is integral to a digitalization initiative that offers real-time visibility of all equipment and facilities through IIoT. This solution has empowered Equinor to anticipate and resolve potential production issues promptly while adjusting well operating parameters based on the required volume of crude oil to be delivered.

The outcomes achieved through this initiative have resulted in a substantial production increase, enhanced the performance of sucker rod pumps, and reduced the frequency of well interventions [40].

6. CONCLUSION

Technology and development have consistently played a pivotal role in advancing the oil and gas industry. Machine Learning emerges as a promising tool, offering a novel and swift methodology to address technical and economic challenges of the petroleum E&P activities.

This tool empowers operators and industry players to meet targets and explore new opportunities. The Sonatrach can benefit from the lessons and projects in the E&P sector utilizing ML techniques and see what the right approaches will be for harnessing and implementing this technology. The focus should be on optimizing operational efficiency, CAPEX, and NPV.

To meet these targets, forging partnerships with high-tech firms specializing in machine learning, big data and AI is deemed necessary for the Sonatrach. Additionally, it's essential to initiate and train

Sonatrach engineers and experts to master this technology. To ensure the effectiveness of ML, upgrading digital infrastructures and data acquisition and transfer systems is imperative.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] T. Haïdar: Digital Barrels: The Rise Of Machine Learning In Oil And Gas, 2017 [Online].
- [2] S. D. Mohaghegh: Oilfield Data Mining, Intelligent Solutions, Inc., 2011.
- [3] A. Baaziz and L. Quoniam: How to Use Big Data technologies to Optimize Operations in Upstream Petroleum Industry, 21st World Petroleum Congress, Moscow, 2014. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5585/iji.v1i1.4>.
- [4] F. Male and J. L. Jensen: Comparison of Permeability Predictions on Cemented Sandstones with Physics-Based and Machine Learning Approaches, Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering, Vol 77, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2020.103244>.
- [5] W.J. Al-Mudhafar: Integrating Well Log Interpretations for Lithofacies Classification and Permeability Modelling Through Advanced Machine Learning Algorithms, Journal of Petroleum Exploration and Production Technology, Vol 7, 2017, pp. 1023-1033. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13202-017-0360-0>.
- [6] F. Liu and A. Patel: Well Failure Detection for Rod Pump Artificial Lift System through Pattern Recognition, International Petroleum Technology Conference, Beijing, China, 2013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2523/IPTC-16578-MS>.
- [7] Y.N. Pandey and A. Rastogi: Machine Learning in the Oil and Gas Industry, 1st Edition, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4842-6094-4>.
- [8] D.A.B. Oliveira and R.S. Ferreira: Interpolating Seismic Data with Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks, IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, Vol 15, No. 12, 2018, pp. 1952-1956. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2018.2866199>.
- [9] L. Mosser and O. Dubrule: Stochastic Seismic Waveform Inversion Using Generative Adversarial Networks as a Geological Prior, Mathematical Geosciences, Vol 52, 2020, pp. 53-79. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11004-019-09832-6>.
- [10] Y. Zeng and K. Jiang: Automatic Seismic Salt Interpretation with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," The Third International Conference on Information System and Data Mining, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1812.01101>.
- [11] S. Li and C. Yang: Seismic Fault Detection Using an Encoder-Decoder Convolutional Neural Network with a Small Training Set, Journal of Geophysics and Engineering, Vol. 16, No. 1, 2019, pp. 175-189. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jge/gxy015>.
- [12] X. Wu and Y. Shi: Convolutional Neural Networks for Fault Interpretation in Seismic Images, SEG International Exposition and Annual Meeting, Anaheim, CA, USA, 2018. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1190/segam2018-2995341.1>.
- [13] B. Hall: Facies Classification Using Machine Learning, The Leading Edge, Vol. 35, No. 10, pp. 906-909, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1190/tle35100906.1>.
- [14] S. Mohaghegh and R. Arefi: Petroleum Reservoir Characterization with the Aid of Artificial Neural Networks, Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering, Vol. 16, No. 4, 1998, pp. 263-274. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-4105\(96\)00028-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-4105(96)00028-9).
- [15] M. Korjani and A. Popa: A New Approach to Reservoir Characterization using Deep Learning Neural Networks, SPE Western Regional Meeting, Anchorage, AK, USA, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/180359-MS>.
- [16] N. Aslam, I. Khan, and A. Alansari: Anomaly Detection Using Explainable Random Forest for the Prediction of Undesirable Events in Oil Wells, Journal of Applied Computational Intelligence and Soft Computing, 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/1558381>.
- [17] H. Zhang, Y. Zeng, and H. Bao: Drilling and Completion Anomaly Detection in Daily Reports by Deep Learning and Natural Language Processing Techniques, Unconventional Resources Technology Conference, Virtual, 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15530/urtec-2020-2885>.

- [18] C.I. Noshi and J.J. Schubert: The Role of Machine Learning in Drilling Operations, SPE/AAPG Eastern Regional Meeting, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, 2018. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2118/191823-18ERM-MS>.
- [19] J. Zhao and Y. Shen: Machine Learning-Based Trigger Detection of Drilling Events Based on Drilling Data, SPE Eastern Regional Meeting, Lexington, KY, USA, 2017. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2118/187512-MS>.
- [20] R. Mohan, A. Hussein and A. Mawlod: Data Driven and AI Methods to Enhance Collaborative Well Planning and Drilling Risk Prediction, Abu Dhabi International Petroleum Exhibition & Conference, Abu Dhabi, UAE, November 2020. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/203073-MS>
- [21] S. Unrau and P. Torriano: Machine Learning Algorithms Applied to Detection of Well Control Events, SPE Kingdom of Saudi Arabia Annual Technical Symposium and Exhibition, Dammam, Saudi Arabia, 2017. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/188104-MS>.
- [22] H. Toreifi and A. Manshad: Prediction and Elimination of Drill String Sticking Using Artificial Intelligence Technique, Heavy Oil, Nova Science Publishers, New York, NY, USA, 2017, pp. 221–241.
- [23] M. A. Dada, M. Mellal, A. Makhoulfi and H. Belhoucet: A Field Development Strategy for the Joint Optimization of Flow Allocations, Well Placements and Well Trajectories, Journal of Energy Exploration & Exploitation, Vol. 39, No. 1, 2020, pp. 502-527. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0144598720974425>.
- [24] S. Bhattacharya and M. Nikolaou: Using Data from Existing Wells to Plan New Wells in Unconventional Gas Field Development, Canadian Unconventional Resources Conference, Calgary, Alberta, Canada, 2011. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2118/147658-MS>.
- [25] S. Bhattacharya and M. Nikolaou: Analysis of Production History for Unconventional Gas Reservoirs with Statistical Methods, SPE Journal, Vol. 18, No. 5, 2013, pp. 878-893. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2118/147658-PA>.
- [26] L. C. Reis: Risk Analysis with History Matching Using Experimental Design or Artificial Neural Networks, SPE Europe/EAGE Annual Conference and Exhibition, Vienna, Austria, 2006. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/100255-MS>.
- [27] A. Shahkarami and S. D. Mohaghegh: Artificial Intelligence (AI) Assisted History Matching, SPE Western North American and Rocky Mountain Joint Meeting, Denver, CO, USA, 2014. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/169507-MS>.
- [28] S. D. Mohaghegh and O. S. Grujic: Modelling, History Matching, Forecasting and Analysis of Shale Reservoirs Performance Using Artificial Intelligence, SPE Digital Energy Conference and Exhibition, Woodlands, TX, USA, 2011. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/143875-MS>.
- [29] J. Rebeschini and M. Querales: Building Neural-Network-Based Models Using Nodal and Time-Series Analysis for Short-Term Production Forecasting, SPE Middle East Intelligent Energy Conference and Exhibition, Manama, Bahrain, 2013. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/167393-MS>.
- [30] J. Sun, X. Ma and M. Kazi: Comparison of Decline Curve Analysis DCA with Recursive Neural Networks RNN for Production Forecast of Multiple Wells, SPE Western Regional Meeting, Garden Grove, CA, USA, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/190104-MS>.
- [31] M. Stundner, G. Zangl and L. Neuhofer: Deployment of a Generic Expert System to Rank Operations Business Opportunities Automatically under Ever-Changing Economic Conditions, SPE Annual Technical Conference and Exhibition, Dubai, UAE, 2016. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/181683-MS>.
- [32] C. Carpenter: Machine Learning Optimizes Production in an Unconventional Reservoir, Journal of Petroleum Technology, Vol. 74, No. 07, 2022, p77-79. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/0722-0077-JPT>.

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- [33] M. G. Shirangi, Y. Oruganti and T. Wilson: Prescriptive Analytics for Completion Optimization in Unconventional Resources, SPE Western Regional Meeting held in San Jose, California, USA, 2019. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/195311-MS>.
- [34] A. Ahmadi and M. Gu: A Robust Workflow for Optimizing Drilling/Completion/Frac Design Using Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, SPE Annual Technical Conference and Exhibition, Houston, Texas, USA, October 2022. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/210160-MS>.
- [35] H. Laoufi, Z. Megherbi and N. Zeraibi: Selection of Sand Control Completion Techniques Using Machine Learning, International Geomechanics Symposium, Abu Dhabi, UAE, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.56952/IGS-2022-118>.
- [36] R. Bharadwaj: AI for Exploration & Production (Upstream) in the Oil and Gas Industry - Current Applications [Online], 2019. <https://emerj.com/ai-sector-overviews/ai-exploration-production-upstream-oil-gas-industry-current-applications/>.
- [37] M. Zborowski: Total, Google Cloud to Team on AI for Upstream, Journal of Petroleum Technology [Online], 2018.
- [38] M. Venables: Artificial Intelligence for Oil & Gas Optimization, Double Eagle Alloys [Online], 2018.
- [39] Gazprom Neft: Gazprom Neft signs Cooperation Agreement with Yandex, Gazprom Neft Press Center [Online], 2017.
- [40] J. Freeman, P. Kulkarni and R. Benoit: Enabling Autonomous Well Optimization via Using IoT-Enabled Devices and Machine Learning in Bakken Horizontal Wells, SPE Artificial Lift Conference and Exhibition - Americas, The Woodlands, Texas, USA, 2018. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2118/190955-MS>.